

Research Article

Design of Diverter less Supersonic Bifurcating Inlet for Increased Thrust and Stealth Characteristics in High Speed Fighter Aircraft

¹A.A.Aswini, ²N.Tamilselvam, ³P.Varalakshmi, ⁴G.P.Clastinmony, ⁵B.Malarvizhi

²Assistant Professor, Department of Aeronautical Engineering, Adhiyamaan College of Engineering, Hosur, Tamilnadu.

^{1, 3, 4, 5} Department of Aeronautical Engineering, Adhiyamaan College of Engineering, Hosur, Tamilnadu

Abstract

The necessity of Fighter Aircrafts to travel faster than the speed of sound has resulted in the development of more complex and sophisticated inlet designs for the modern day fighters. Depending on the application various types of Supersonic inlet configurations such as Pitot intake, Bell mouth Intake, Serpentine Intakes, etc., are used. Design of a simple supersonic intake is strongly dependent upon the Total Pressure Recovery and the flow uniformity at the face of the compressor. The present study is focused on the design and analysis of Diverter less Supersonic Bifurcating Inlet for and their performance comparison. A numerical model is being developed. The performance of the Inlet design is to be analysed using CFD

Keywords: *Supersonic inlets, total pressure, Diverter less Supersonic Bifurcating inlet.*

1. Introduction

As aircraft continue to evolve, the requirements for their development are becoming more and more stringent. For military applications, the overall thrust to weight ratio requirement is increasing, demanding either lighter aircraft through length reductions or lighter materials, or more powerful engines which tend to add weight. By reducing the overall aircraft length, large weight savings may be realized with an increase in overall thrust to weight ratio for the same engines. A reduction in weight leads to lower costs and lighter, more compact high performance aircraft.

Reduction in radar cross-section is another area of design focus. With advancements in radar technology, it is necessary to continue to decrease the radar cross-section (RCS) of aircraft. Many technologies have been developed which decrease the radar cross section of an aircraft. A large reduction in RCS can be realized by eliminating the engine fan face as a radar return source. The fan face can be hidden from radar by developing an inlet duct that is offset so that there is no direct line of sight from the entrance of the inlet duct to the engine fan face. This prevents a direct path for radar beams to strike the

engine fan face and return to the receiver. These ducts are included in a general class of serpentine inlet ducts. Serpentine inlet ducts have been in existence for some time and can be found in many of today's

commercial and military aircraft including the Boeing 727, F-16 and F-117. Commercial aircraft use serpentine ducts to allow the thrust vector from rear mounted engines to be aligned with the axis of the aircraft. The developments in technology and reduction in radar cross section requirements are leading. serpentine inlet ducts that are shorter and have larger height offsets throughout the duct. To improve aircraft thrust to weight ratio, the serpentine shape of the inlet duct is becoming more aggressive as an ultra-compact, highly offset inlet duct, allowing a reduction in the overall aircraft length. While these inlet ducts reduce the radar cross section, they also reduce the stability margin of the propulsion system. The more aggressive inlet ducts result in increased turning which in turn produces secondary flow within the duct. The compact nature of the duct limits the length for diffusion and dissipation of these secondary flows and leads to greater distortion levels at the engine fan face. This inlet distortion can produce a reduction in stability margin for the compressor or fan of the turbine engine. In addition, inlet distortion can result in high cycle fatigue, which may lead to catastrophic loss of aircraft, loss of aircraft operability, and increased maintenance costs.

2. Diverter less Supersonic Inlet

A diverter less supersonic inlet (DSI) is a type of jet engine air intake used by some modern combat aircraft to control air flow into their engines. It consists of a "bump" and a forward-swept inlet cowl, which work together to divert boundary layer airflow away from the aircraft's engine while compressing the air to slow it down from supersonic speed. The DSI can be used to replace conventional methods of controlling supersonic and boundary layer airflow. DSI's have been tested on F-16's for speeds of up to Mach 2 and can be used to replace the intake ramp and inlet cone, which are more complex, heavy and expensive.

Tactical aircraft pose a formidable challenge for inlet designers. A fighter inlet must provide an engine with high-quality airflow over a wide range of speeds, altitudes, and manoeuvring conditions while accommodating the full range of engine airflow from idle to maximum military or afterburning power. The inlet designer must also consider the constraints imposed by configuration features, such as nose landing gears, weapon bays, equipment access panels, and fore body shaping. The design must produce the lowest drag, lowest weight, lowest cost, and highest propulsion performance. It must also meet stringent low observable requirements.

Historically, inlet complexity is a function of top speed for fighter aircraft. Higher Mach numbers require more sophisticated devices for compressing supersonic airflow to slow it down to subsonic levels before it reaches the face of the engine. (Jet engines are not designed to handle the shock waves associated with supersonic airflow.)

These compression schemes involve the conversion of the kinetic energy of the supersonic airstream into total pressure on the compressor face of the engine. Speeds over Mach 2 generally require more elaborate compression schemes. The F-15 inlet, for example, contains a series of movable compression ramps and doors controlled by software and elaborate mechanical systems. The ramps move to adjust the external and internal shape of the inlet to provide the optimum airflow to the engine at various aircraft speeds and angles of attack. Doors and ducting allow excess airflow to bypass the inlet.

Inlet designs for fighter aircraft must also account for a layer of low-energy air that forms on the surface of the fuselage at subsonic and supersonic speeds. (These layers also form on the inlet compression surfaces.) This layer of slow moving, turbulent air, called a boundary layer, can create chaos when disturbed by the shock waves created by the inlet. The result can be unwanted airflow distortions at the engine face. If the shock wave/boundary layer interaction is severe enough, the engine will stall. The boundary layer thickens with increased speed and increased forebody distance, the length from the nose of the airplane to the inlet itself.

The DSI bump functions as a compression surface and creates a pressure distribution that prevents the majority of the boundary layer air from entering the inlet at speeds up to Mach 2. In essence, the DSI does away with complex and heavy mechanical systems.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Modelling

The Diverter less inlet has designed by using the CATIA V5 and then it's imported in the ANSYS FLUENT software which is shown in figure 1. The drafting diagrams are shown in the Figure 2. In that figure the front view, side view, top view and cross sectional views of inlet are shown clearly.

Figure (1) Isometric View of Diverter Less Inlet

Figure (2) Orthographic views of Diverter less inlet

3.2 Finite Element Modelling and Analysis

The 2D Analysis has done by the ANSYS FLUENT software. Further step of analysing is Meshing. Meshing has done by ICEM CFD.

All CFD problems are defined in terms of initial and boundary conditions. The most common boundary conditions that are used in finite volume methods are,

Figure (3) meshing of Diverter Less Inlet

Figure (5) Velocity contour

- ❖ Inlet Boundary Conditions –Pressure farfield.
- ❖ Outlet Boundary Conditions-pressure outlet.
- ❖ Wall Boundary Conditions-constant temperature no slip wall.
- ❖ Diverterless Design- Specified shear wall.
- ❖ Model- Viscous (SplartAlmaraus or K-Epsilon)

The pressure contour is shown in the figure 4. It is clearly explains that the pressure got increase at the end. So the velocity of the air which enters into the compressor got reduce. This condition will give the high thrust. And the velocity contour is shown in figure 5. It explains that the decreasing velocity of the inlet for increasing the thrust. Finally the inlet model analysis got successful. And the analysis report compared with the experimental results.

4. Conclusion

The DSI bump functions as a compression surface and creates a pressure distribution that prevents the majority of the boundary layer air from entering the inlet at speeds up to Mach 2. In essence, the DSI does away with complex and heavy mechanical systems

The Diverter less Supersonic Inlet has following Advantages

- Relatively Simple Design
- Less Drag
- Very Low Radar Cross Section
- Increased Total Pressure Recovery at Off-Design Conditions.

5. References

1. Hehs, Eric (15 July 2000). "JSF Diverterless Supersonic Inlet". *Code One magazine*. Lockheed Martin. Retrieved 11 February 2011.
2. Hehs, Eric. "JSF Diverterless Supersonic Inlet." *Code One Magazine*. Retrieved 28 December 2012.
3. "Fast History: Lockheed's Diverterless Supersonic Inlet Testbed F-16" *aviationintel.com*, 13 January 2013
4. Hehs, Eric. "JSF Diverterless Supersonic Inlet." *LockMart*, 15 July 2000.
5. "J-20's Stealth Signature Poses Interesting Unknowns." *Aviation Week*. Retrieved 13 January 2013
6. "JL-9 Trainer Jet gets DSI inlet, Guizhou China". *AirForceWorld.com*. Retrieved 29 Aug 2011.
7. "Paris Air Show 2011 - Naval air trainer unveiled by Chinese media". *home.janes.com*, 15 February 2012.
8. "PM to select Sanskrit name for LCA on May 4". 27 April 2003. Archived from the original on 27 September 2011. Retrieved 30 June 2014.
9. Generators". *Proceedings Of the 37th National & 4th International Conference on Fluid Mechanics and Fluid Power*.16–18 December 2010. Archivedfrom the original on 1 July 2014. Retrieved 1 July 2014.